

PUSHKARA NAVAMSA

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Cite This Article: Dr. N. G. Kumaran, “Pushkara Navamsa”, International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 1-3, 2023.

Abstract:

The Vedic astrology uses many techniques to assess the strength or the weakness of a planet or the planets, so that the beneficial effects and the malefic outcomes offered by them can be predicted and measured. The concept of the Pushkara Navamsa is one such a method. It is simple, self-explanatory and at the same time a strong indicator. It does not require any great calculation to identify the Pushkara Navamsa. This study carries the significant aspects of the Pushkara Navamsa and its contributory role in the astrological predictions.

Key Words: Pushkara Navamsa, Nakshtra Pada, Beneficial Placements, Strength of the Planet

Pushkara Navamsa:

The horoscope is a basic representation of the planets in a chart like fashion and it is called as the Natal chart or the Birth chart of the Rasi division. It is denoted by the letter D 1. It is the mapping of the transiting planets at the exact time of a birth or at the time of occurrence of an event. The position of the planets is plotted according to the degree wise placement or according to the quarter of the star in which they are placed. The Almanacs are used to trace down the movements and the positions of the planets for locating and plotting them. Each division in the Rasi chart or the Zodiac circle consists of 30 degrees and there are 12 such equal divisions. When the 30 degrees are divided by 9 we get 12 equal parts and each part is called as a Navamsa division. There are totally 108 Navamsa divisions. The Navam means the number 9. These are placed in 12 zodiac boxes of 3 degrees and 20 minutes each and this chart is called as the Navamsa division and it is denoted by the symbol D 9. A planet placed strong in the Rasi chart should be well placed in the Navamsa chart also. Otherwise, the planet is considered as powerless and its strength in the D 1 chart is not valued or considered. The ability to give good results will be affected if a planet is not placed stronger in the D 9 chart. If the Rasi chart or the D 1 can be compared to a flower, then the Navamsa chart D 9 can be said to be the fragrance of the flower. These two charts are inseparable.

The Pushkara in the Sanskrit language means the Sacred. We must have heard about the words Pushkarani or the Holy water tanks or holy rivers in the temples. Here also the word Pushkara means the Valuable worthy and auspicious. There are totally 24 Pushkara Navamsa points among the 108 Navamsa divisions which are noteworthy and called as the Pushkara Navamsa points or degrees or places. Each rasi division consisting of two Pushkara Navamsa degrees. Of the nine planets, the stars of the Mars, the Mercury and the Ketu do not possess the Pushkara Navamsa points. There are 6 Pushkara Navamsa places for the stars of the Sun. Similarly, there are 6 places for the stars of the Jupiter. Three star pada for each of the three star pada of the Venus, the Saturn, the Moon and the Rahu respectively. So totally there are 24 Pushkara Navamsa points and they are evenly distributed among the 12 zodiac signs, with each sign carrying two Pushkara Navamsa points. The 24 Pushkara Navamsa star pada are tabulated below for better clarity and understanding. It can be observed that the Pushkara Navamsa are placed in the houses of the auspicious planets like the Moon, the Mercury, the Jupiter and the Venus only in the Navamsa chart D 9. When the Pushkara Navamsa is placed in the 6th, 8th and 12th to the sign where it is placed in the Rasi chart, it will give adverse effects also at the same time when it bestows name and fame to the native.

The 24 Pushkara Navamsa points are categorized as follows.

- In Vargottama status of Pushkara Navamsa3 stages.
- In favourable status of Pushkara Navamsa..... 5 stages.
- In unfavourable status of Pushkara Navamsa5 stages.
- In mixed status of Pushkara Navamsa11 stages.

Total 24 stages

S.No	Sign and Sign Lord	Star and Star Lord	Star and Star Lord
1	Aries, Mars	Bharani 3, (41 Arietis) Venus	Karthika 1, (Pleades) Sun
2	Taurus, Venus	Karthika 4, (Pleades) Sun	Rohini 2, (Aldebaran) Moon
3	Gemini, Mercury	Ardra 4, (Betageuse) Rahu	Punarvasu 2, (Castor and Pollux) Jupiter
4	Cancer, Moon	Punarvasu 4(Castor and Pollux), Jupiter	Pushya 2, (Cancri) Saturn
5	Leo, Sun	Purva phalguni 3, Zosma Leonis) Venus	Uthra Phalguni 1, (Denibola) Sun

6	Virgo, Mercury	Uthra Phalguni 3, (Denibola) Sun	Hastha 2, (Corvi) Moon
7	Libra. Venus	Swathi 4, (Arcturus) Rahu	Vishaka 2, (Librae) Jupiter
8	Scorpio, Mars	Anuradha 2, (Scorpionis) Saturn	Vishaka 4, (Librae) Jupiter
9	Sagittarius, Jupiter	Poorvashada 3, (Kaus Australis) Venus	Uthrashada 1, (Nunki) Sun
10	Capricorn, Saturn	Uthrashada 4, (Nunki), Venus	Shravan 2, (Aquilae) Moon
11	Aquarius, Saturn	Sadhabishek 4, (Aquarii) Rahu	Purva Bhadra pada 2, (Pegasi) Jupiter
12	Pisces, Jupiter	Purva Bhadra pada 4, (Pegasi) Jupiter	Uthra Bhadra pada 3, (Andromedae) Saturn

When a planet is placed in D 1 chart in the respective quarter of the star mentioned herein the tabular column, it will be placed in the Pushkara Navamsa degree in the Navamsa D 9 chart. This is how the Pushkara Navamsa is created and constructed. It is to be noted that the planet placed in the Pushkara Navamsa will bestow auspicious results during its Dasa or the Bhukthi periods. The placement of Pushkara Navamsa can be also understood in the following method also. For the Fiery signs of the Aries, the Leo and the Sagittarius, the Pushkara Navamsa points are the 7th and the 9th division of their Navamsa divisions. For the Earthly signs of the Taurus, the Virgo and the Capricorn, their 3rd and 5th Navamsa divisions form as the Pushkara Navamsa. For the Airy signs of the Gemini, the Libra and the Aquarius, the 6th and the 8th Navamsa divisions are termed as the Pushkara Navamsa points. For the Watery signs of the Cancer, the Scorpio and the Pisces, their 1st and the 3rd Navamsa divisions are classified as the Pushkara Navamsa divisions.

S.No	Name	Pushkara Navamsa Points
1	Mahatma Gandhi	3 planets
2	Swami Vivekananda	2 planets and Ascendant
3	LalBahadur Sastri	2 planets
4	Sardhar Vallabhai Patel	2 planets
5	Mother Teresa	2 planets
6	Atal Bihari Vajpayee	1 planet
7	Lal Kishan Advani	2 planets
8	Indira Gandhi	2 planets
9	A. P. J. Abdul Kalam	1 planet
10	V.P. Singh	2 planets
11	M. G. Ramachandran	2 planets and Ascendant
12	J. Jayalalithaa	1 planet and Ascendant
13	N. T. Rama Rao	4 planets and Ascendant
14	Narendra Modi	3 planets and Ascendant
15	M. S. Dhoni	3 planets and Ascendant
16	Kamal Haasan	2 planets and Ascendant
17	Amitabh Bacchan	2 planets
18	Rajesh Khanna	2 planets
19	Sivaji Ganesan	1 planet and Ascendant
20	P. Chidambaram	2 planets

Case Study:

Shri N. T. Rama Rao, Actor, Former Chief Minister of Andhra Pradesh. Shri N. T. Rama Rao was born on 28/05/1923 at 16 43 I.S.T. at Machelepatnam, Andhra Pradesh.

	Venus	Sun Mercury ®	Mars
Ketu	Rasi D 1 Chart		Rahu
		Asc, Moon Jupiter®	Saturn® Mandhi

His birth star was Swathi and he was born with the Libra ascendant with the balance of Rahu Dasa for about one year and seven months. If his horoscope is analysed it has been identified that the Ascendant, the Moon, the Mercury, the Jupiter and the Ketu are placed in the Pushkara Navamsa points. The Moon, the Jupiter and the Ascendant are all placed in the star of the Swathi in the fourth quarter. The Mercury is placed in the star of the Rohini in the second quarter of it. The Ketu is placed in the 2nd quarter of Poorva Bhadra Pada. All these are Pushkara Navamsa star quarters.

Because of the beneficial aspects of the Pushkara Navamsa in his natal chart, Shri N. T. Rama Rao attained glory, wealth and even the Power. He was the undisputed hero the Telugu filmdom for many decades. He has acted as Lord Rama and as Lord Krishna in many of his mythological movies. People even worshiped

him as their divine hero. Later in his life he left the film industry and started his own political party and became the Chief Minister of the Andhra Pradesh. But, at the same time, the successful events bestowed by the Pushkara Navamsa did not carry him through his entire life. He had to struggle to maintain his Chief Minister chair and his personal life in the later stages of life were muddled with controversies and damaged his hitherto heroic image and status. This is because in the Navamsa chart D 9, the ascendant, the Moon and the Jupiter were placed in the 6th house, the Pisces, to the D 1 ascendant Libra. The Mercury and the Ketu, the other two Pushkara Navamsa points were placed in the 8th house the Taurus. This gave him a Saint like life and even he started wearing the robes like that of the ascetic person and he called himself as Raja Sanyasi, (the Royal saint). Generally, the planets under the Pushkara Navamsa are supposed to bless with good effects and auspicious events in life. But, at the same time, the nature of the planets placed in the Pushkara Navamsa, the houses the Pushkara Navamsa falls, the associated planets etc., decide the final or the total outcome of the Pushkara Navamsa.

Effects of the Pushkara Navamsa:

Generally, the astrological texts prescribe that the planets placed in the Pushkara Navamsa will give auspicious and beneficial results during their dasa and bhukthi periods. For example, when the Jupiter is placed in the Pushkara Navamsa it bestows the native with good qualities, honour, name and fame, the riches, disciplined life and good progeny. Among the 24 Pushkara Navamsa degree points, three entities gain more significance and considered to be more powerful and flourishing. They are the 2nd quarter of the Rohini, the 4th quarter of the Punarvasu and the 1st quarter of the Uthrashada stars. This is because these three points attain Vargottama status. The Vargottama is a stage in astrology where the ascendant or any planet is placed in the same sign both in the D1 chart and in the D 9 chart. The effect of the planet which has attained the Vargottama is said to be equivalent to the exalted state of it. The 2nd quarter of the Rohini is placed in the sign of Taurus both in the Rasi and in the Navamsa charts. The 4th quarter of the Punarvasu is situated in the sign of the Cancer both in the D and in the D 9 charts. The Uthrashada 1st quarter is located in the sign of the Sagittarius both in the Rasi and in the Navamsa charts.

Conclusion:

We have seen the basis of the Pushkara Navamsa and its nature of functioning in the natal chart in order to yield positive as well as negative results. More research is needed in identifying the effects of the Pushkara Navamsa in the astrological predictions. In future, we shall try to present in depth analysis and more interesting case studies in this regard.

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